

Syrian Priestesses (Emar, Mari, Ugarit)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Babylonian Religions, Ancient Syrian Religion

city - time period LBA

Date Range: 1800 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: Syria BA

Region tags: Middle East, Lebanon, Levant, Mesopotamia, Syria

Mari, Emar and Ugarit sites, nowadays in modern Syria

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Michel, P., 2016, « Syrian Priestess in the Late Bronze Age », in S. Budin (éd.) *Women in Antiquity : Real Women Across the Ancient World*, Routledge Press, Abingdon UK, New York, p. 441-452.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/installationofba0000flem>

– Source 1 Description: <https://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/propylaeumdok/6152/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/emarkonk/index.html>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: In LBA Emar, cultural and religious contacts are attested with Hittite Anatolia

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, the priestess could be the king's daughter: in Mari for example we know about Samsî-Addu who made one of his daughters, namely Kunsîm-Mâtum, priestess of Dagan in Terqa (MARI 4, 1985, 389-390).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Je ne sais pas

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Temples have been excavated in Mari, in Emar as well as in Ugarit.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Oui

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Uniquement l'espace public religieux

– Certains espaces publics

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Oui

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Oui

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Oui

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Je ne sais pas

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Oui

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - Oui
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - Je ne sais pas
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - Non
- ↳ Humans:
 - Oui
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - Je ne sais pas

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Non

Notes: See for example: https://www.worldhistory.org/trans/fr/2-701/croyances-en-lau-dela-dans-lancienne-mesopotamie/#google_vignette "Il convient de souligner que les notions mésopotamiennes de corps physique et d'êtemmu ne représentent pas un dualisme strict entre le corps et l'âme."

Belief in afterlife:

– Oui

Notes: The ancient Mesopotamians conceived of the afterlife as the cosmic opposite of the heavens, and as an obscure version of life on earth.

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - Oui

- ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
 - Oui

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: no tombs of priestess has been found, so it is impossible to know.

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Concerning the entu-priestess in Emar for example, a new entu was nominated only after the death of the previous one.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Oui

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: This question needs comments: the status of the ugbatum (Sumerian ERES.DINGIR) prohibited her from marriage. The Naditum (Sumerian LUKUR) could marry but was not permitted to bear children. The entu (Sumerian also ERES.DINGIR but with higher status than the ugbatum) was a high-ranking priestess who has made a vow of chastity. The mas'artu in Emar could have children (as attested in some legal documents and contracts). Finally, the Qadistum (Sumerian NU.GIG) could marry and have children. We see then that rules were different from a function to another, from a place to another and from a status to another.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: or not allowed to marry, or chastity mandatory.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Le champ ne sait pas

Notes: we imagine that it was the case

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Le champ ne sait pas

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Non

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Non

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Je ne sais pas

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: On the occasion of the gallubu for the Installation of the Entu of Baal in Emar, the priestess's head was shaved.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: During the malluku, i.e. installation of the entu of Baal in Emar, a red garment was used.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: for the malluku of the entu of Baal in Emar, a veil was used and jewels were used for the priestess.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– Je ne sais pas

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Oui

Notes: with the Royal power.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Syrian Priestesses (Emar, Mari, Ugarit), Niehr, Herbert. "Daniel E. Fleming, the Installation of Baal's High Priestess at Emar. (harvard Semitic Studies 42). Atlanta Georgia (scholars Press) 1992. XVII + 348 Seiten. ISBN 1-55540-726-9." 40, no. 2 (September 22, 1996). <https://doi.org/10.1163/25890468-04002033>.

Reference: Syrian Priestesses (Emar, Mari, Ugarit), YAMADA, Masamichi. "<i>because She Is a Daughter of Emar</i>," 51, no. 0 (March 30, 2016). <https://doi.org/10.5356/orient.51.111>.

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Reference: Syrian Priestesses (Emar, Mari, Ugarit), Lion, Brigitte. "Daniel E. Fleming, Time at Emar. The Cultic Calendar and the Rituals from the Diviner's Archive , Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake, 2000" Vol. 94, no. 2 (September 1, 2001). <https://doi.org/10.3917/assy.094.0181b>.

Reference: Syrian Priestesses (Emar, Mari, Ugarit), Michel, Patrick. *Le Culte Des Pierres À Emar À L'époque Hittite*. Fribourg: OBO 266, 2014.